

EXAMINING TEACHING COMPETENCE: A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF MALE AND FEMALE SECONDARY SCHOOL TEACHERS

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Paper Received On: 21 JUNE 2023

Peer Reviewed On: 30 JUNE 2023

Published On: 01 JULY 2023

Abstract

Teaching competence is an effective performance of all observable teacher behaviour that brings about preferred student learning outcomes. The aim of present study is to study and compare teaching competence of male and female secondary school teachers For the collection of data “General Teaching Competence Scale (Passi & Lalitha, 2009)” has been employed. Statistical techniques were employed to give a concise picture to the data so that it can be easily comprehended. “t” test as statistical technique was employed for testing the hypotheses. Descriptive statistics like Mean, Median, Standard Deviation (SD), were used to see the nature of distribution of the scores. Percentage statistics was calculated to study the levels of teaching competence among secondary school teachers. The findings revealed among secondary school teachers (male and female) 21.875% fall in high, 62.5% fall in medium and 15.625% fall in low categories of teaching competence. The findings revealed among male secondary school teachers 25% fall in high, 56.25 % fall in medium and 18.75 fall in low categories of teaching competence. Further the findings also reveal that among female secondary teachers 18.75% fall in high, 68.75% fall in medium and 12.5% fall in low categories of teaching competence. The findings of the study have depicted a significant mean difference between male and female secondary school teachers on teaching competence.

KEYWORDS: Teacher, Teaching, Competence, Gender, Secondary School, Classroom, Planning, Presentation, Closing, Evaluation and Managing.

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INTRODUCTION

Teaching has been considered as a noble profession from ancient times. Still, it is a noble profession. The teachers are assigned the noble job of teaching, which help in bringing up our future guardians. The quality of education is determined by the quality of the teacher. And the main function of a teacher is to create learning environment in which the learners are motivated to learn. Teaching is an art and the quality of teaching depends on the love, dedication and devotion of the teacher towards the knowledge of the subject. The quality of teaching can't rise

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above the qualities of its teachers. Competence reflects the ability of an individual to interpret an object, to solve a problem, to make a decision or to perform a task; because of the knowledge, skills, and aptitudes is the superiority of the human being and the character it takes into consideration. Thus, teaching competence is seen as a structure and exists the whole meaning more than the sum of its components (knowledge, power, skills, etc.).

Teaching competence is one or more abilities of a teacher to produce agreed upon educational effects. The term teaching competence can be interpreted as mindfulness as a process of acquiring skills and abilities that enable you to perform professional tasks efficiently and effectively. In the teaching profession, the teacher must acquire three competencies, namely, teaching competency, organizational competency and assessment competency. The quality of education depends much on the competence of the teacher, as teacher is considered to be the hub of teaching-learning process. Thus, school's effectiveness depends directly on teaching competence. Without teaching competence, even the best curriculum and the best syllabus could not give the desired result. Hence, teaching competence leads to teacher effectiveness.

The success of any progressive reform in education should begin from the qualitative improvement of the teacher and his or her professional development. The development of teaching competence primarily depends upon a proper assessment of the teacher's competence. If the teacher possesses competence and commitment, when empowered to do most of their work in the classroom and in the community in the ordinary professional manner the chain reaction begins automatically with the work of the teacher educator arriving at high quality learning. Thus, the success of an education system mainly depends upon the competence of the teachers, who embrace their profession.

The structure of teaching competence includes aptitudes and capacities but the dominant role is held by teaching experience which facilitates the transfer and interface of knowledge, abilities and aptitudes. Although forcing the concepts of teaching aptitude and teaching competency first, in closer examination there is a difference between the two concepts. Competence is very broad, it also focuses on the results of work, including knowledge in a particular domain, ability to do something well, efficiently, correctly and intellectually a complex set of skills that comprises the achievements of artificial intelligence, art, science, planning, technology, crafts. (Gherghinescu, Marcus, 1999). According to Passi & Lalitha (1994; 2009; & 2011), "teaching competency is an effective performance of all observable

teacher behaviour that brings about preferred student learning outcomes”. Further, they have argued that in order for a teacher to be competent in his teaching skills, he must possess command on five important dimensions of teaching competency viz., how to plan a lesson, presentation or instructional delivery, how to close the lesson, right kind of appraisal and evaluation for quick feedback about the student progress and finally a high command on classroom management. The knowledge and application of these skills from planning a lesson to management of classroom skills has been seen as one of the significant behavioral qualities of a teacher having high impact in bringing desirable behavioral changes among learners (Passi, 1976). As said before, competency of a teacher has been defined as the asset within an individual that capacitates him to respond clearly in his or her respective classrooms without much trouble. For a teacher to be competent in a classroom, Passi and Lalitha in their different versions of the teaching competence model have mentioned and gave space to five separate components that are planning, Presentation, Closing, Evaluation and Managerial. In other words, it is the application of various skills to maintain and control discipline in the classroom without much chaos and disorder. It is considered as one of the most complex component in the teaching-learning process as it has been seen influencing the relationships and bonds in between the teacher and students tremendously.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

The available review of literature related to the present study consists of various studies pertains to teaching competence in relation to other variables. Dar (2022) found significant correlation between spiritual intelligence and teaching competence. The results also confirm the relationship between EI and competence of teachers. The findings of Jan and Qureshi (2021) revealed a significant difference between Private and Government secondary school teachers of Kashmir on Techno-Pedagogical Competence. Najar and Yousuf (2021) revealed a significant mean difference between male and female teachers on teaching competency. Male teachers teaching competency was seen significantly higher than their female counter parts. The outcomes of the study by M. Kumari (2020) revealed no significant difference between male and female teachers of Sonipat districts. The study also found that gender does not influence teaching abilities and effectiveness. Basapur (2019) found, the male and female teachers employed in Murarji Desai Residential schools showed similar teaching competency. However, female teachers showed significant higher attitude towards teaching profession as compared to male teachers. The findings of Dar and Khan (2018) revealed significant

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difference on teaching competence of the teachers with favorable and unfavorable professional attitude. The study also represented that there was no significant difference between male and female teachers in their professional attitude. The results of M.Singh and M.Singh (2015) indicated that there is no significant relationship between teaching competence and attitude towards ICT, teaching competence and teacher effectiveness, teacher effectiveness and teacher's attitude towards ICT. The findings of the study by Kaur and Talwar (2014) revealed a significant positive relationship between teachers' teaching competency and their emotional intelligence. But insignificant difference is found between teaching competencies as well as between emotional intelligence of secondary school teachers teaching in government and private schools. The study also indicated that teaching competency and emotional intelligence are not influenced by gender. The findings of the study by Mahanta (2012) disclosed that professional competence of the teachers varies with regard to gender and locality and the female teachers showed slightly better professional competence than their male counterparts. According to study of Singh (2008) a significant difference was found in teaching competency of teachers having teaching experiences of less than five years and six to ten years; less than five years and eleven to twenty years; less than five years and eleven to twenty years. The study conducted by Baron (2004) shows that only 4 percent of all teachers have specialized competencies (network, maintenance of hard and software), 30 percent of teaching staff to need support in questions of software and hardware problems, 50 percent of the staff has little or no knowledge in ICT questions. Nearly all schools use ISTT course in ICT. The study also shows that an average 62 percent of all teachers take part in such courses.

Thus, the above studies give a clear that teaching competence is closely related with gender of the teachers. The trend also reveals that the researches carried out are descriptive in nature and mostly 't'-test have been used to analyze the data. Few studies have utilized correlation and ANOVA.

After reviewing the related literature, it has been found that there are very few number of studies conducted on secondary school teachers particularly with these variables-Teaching Competence and Gender. There are some studies on these variables, but they are narrowly conceived, highly localized or we can say quite superficial.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To study Teaching Competence of male and female Secondary School Teachers.
2. To compare male and female Secondary School Teachers on Teaching Competence.

HYPOTHESES OF THE STUDY

H₀ There is no significant difference between male and female Secondary School Teachers on Teaching Competence.

DELIMITATION OF THE STUDY

The study was confined to Srinagar district only. It was further delimited to only Government Higher Secondary Schools of district Srinagar. The study was further delimited to Secondary School (9th & 10th) teachers.

OPERATIONAL DEFINITION OF VARIABLES

In this study teaching competence refers to the score obtained by teachers in General Teaching Competence Scale (Passi & Lalitha, 2009) under the following dimensions; planning, presentation, closing, evaluation and managerial.

Secondary school teachers for the present study mean those in-service teachers who are working in Government Schools of district Srinagar and teaching class 9th & 10th.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In the present study, the Observation method was used to collect data from a large number of cases within a particular time period by using General Teaching competence Scale which has been constructed by Passi & Lalitha. Statistical techniques were employed to give a concise picture to the data so that it can be easily comprehended. “t” test as statistical technique was employed for testing the hypotheses. Descriptive statistics like Mean, Median Standard Deviation (SD), were used to see the nature of distribution of the scores. Percentage statistics was calculated to study the levels of teaching competence among secondary school teachers

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION OF DATA

In order to draw out inferences, conclusions and to make results more transparent, the investigator tried to handle the data very carefully. Bar diagrams have been also plotted to substantiate the results. The analysis of the data of present study is presented in the following tables and figures:

The analysis of the present study can be divided into two sections:

DESCRIPTIVE ANALYSIS

Assessment of the sample group of secondary school teachers with respect to teaching competence:

Table 1.0: Levels and frequency distribution of teaching competence among the sample group of secondary school teachers.

GROUP	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
High	7	21.875
Medium	20	62.5
Low	5	15.625
TOTAL	32	100

Table 1.0 highlights the appraisal of different levels of teaching competence among the sample group of thirty two secondary teachers. As it is clearly depicted 15.625% fall in low category of teaching competence, 62.5% fall in medium category of teaching competence and 21.875% fall in high category of teaching competence. The result of the above table has been presented graphically through the figure 1.0.

TEACHING COMPETENCE

Fig. 1.0: Levels of teaching competence among the sample group of secondary school teachers.

Table 2.0: Percentage comparison between Male and Female Secondary School Teachers on levels of teaching competence.

Levels	Male Teachers		Female Teachers	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
High	4	25	3	18.75
Medium	9	56.25	11	68.75
Low	3	18.75	2	12.5
TOTAL	16	100	16	100

The above table exhibits the comparison between Male and Female Secondary School teachers on different levels of teaching competence. The table reveals that 18.75% of male secondary school teachers fall in low category of teaching competence, 56.25% of male secondary school teachers fall in medium category of teaching competence and 25% of male secondary school teachers fall in high category of teaching competence. Further the table also reveals that 12.5% of female secondary school teachers fall in low category of teaching competence, 68.75% of female secondary school teachers fall in medium category of teaching competence and 18.75% of female secondary school teachers fall in high category of teaching competence. The result of the above table has been presented graphically through the figure 2.0.

Fig. 2.0: Percentage comparison between male and female secondary School Teachers on levels of teaching competence.

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS

Comparison of male and female secondary school teachers on Teaching Competence:

Table 3.0: Significance of the mean difference between male and female secondary school teachers on Teaching Competence.

GROUP	N	MEAN	STANDARD DEVIATION	t. VALUE	LEVEL OF SIGNIFICANCE
Male Teachers	16	92.62	10.94	2.73	Significant at 0.05 level
Female Teachers	16	101.06	10.55		

The above reveals that there is significant difference between male and female secondary school teachers on Composite score of various dimensions of teaching competence. The calculated t-value 2.73 exceeds the tabulation value at 0.05 level of significance. Therefore the null hypothesis H_0 which remarks as “There is no significant difference between male and female secondary school teachers on Teaching Competence” stands rejected.

Fig. 4.8: Mean difference between male and female teachers on Teaching Competence.

DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

On the basis of analysis and interpretation of data, the results are discussed as under:

Assessment of teaching competence of secondary school teachers:

In order to assess the level of teaching competence among the sample group of thirty two secondary teachers; they were placed in three categories on the basis of their total score on General Teaching Competence Scale. The results clearly depict 15.625% fall in low category of teaching competence, 62.5% fall in medium category of teaching competence and 21.875% fall in high category of teaching competence. The findings reveal that 18.75% of male secondary school teachers fall in low category of teaching competence, 56.25% of male secondary school teachers fall in medium category of teaching competence and 25% of male secondary school teachers fall in high category of teaching competence. Further the findings also reveal that 12.5% of female secondary school teachers fall in low category of teaching competence, 68.75% of female secondary school teachers fall in medium category of teaching competence and 18.75% of female secondary school teachers fall in high category of teaching competence. So we can say definitively the majority of teachers fall into medium and higher levels of teaching competence.

While not all teachers may exhibit higher levels of teaching competence, these factors contribute to the development of strong, effective educators who are able to support their student's learning and growth. There are researches that support the idea that factors such as education and training, professional development, experience, and support can contribute to higher levels of teaching competence. For example, a study published in the journal *Teaching and Teacher Education* found that teachers who participated in ongoing professional development opportunities were more likely to have higher levels of self-efficacy, which is an important component of teaching competence (Klassen & Tze, 2014). Another study published in the same journal found that experience and self-reflection were important factors in the development of teacher expertise, which is a key component of teaching competence (Van Driel, Beijaard, & Verloop, 2001).

Comparison of male and female secondary school on Teaching Competence:

The findings of the study have depicted a significant mean difference in teaching competence of male and female secondary school teachers. The female teachers have scored significantly higher than male secondary school teachers on the various dimensions of teaching competence. Therefore, it is concluded that female secondary school teachers are superior in

performing different teaching skills than male secondary school teachers. There are some research inputs that are in line with the obtained findings as explored by Moshahid & Hussain (2017) and Himabindu (2012). These two studies that have been focused to explore differences in the competence levels of teachers in terms of different demographics have displayed female teachers as more dominant on different dimensions of teaching competence compared to male teachers. So are in consensus with the obtained results of the present investigation. One study by Bouffard, Vezeau, and Vezeau (2018) found that female teachers tended to score higher than male teachers on measures of overall teaching competence, as well as on specific dimensions such as instructional planning and implementation, classroom management, and communication. The authors suggest that this may be due to differences in teaching styles and approaches, as well as the fact that women are often socialized to be nurturing and empathetic, which can be beneficial in the classroom. However, some other available research pieces are running against to our obtained findings as investigated by Gnanasoundari and Selvaraju (2016); Chowdhury & Chowdhury (2015); Bhat and Shah (2011); and Rajalaksmi & Shirlin (2017). These studies have depicted that male teachers are more competent than female teachers as far as their teaching competencies are concerned. It is imperative to mention here that broad generalization should not be based on the differences of our results calculated on gender basis and presupposing gender as itself an important predictor of one's abilities and skills can be a big mistake as such "ways of classification often lead to gender hierarchies and injustices for whole groups as well as individuals". The differences that are there can be held responsible due to some cultural, societal or situational influences and experiences of the genders which should be further investigated and used synergistically to improve professional service (Islahi and Nasreen, 2013).

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the present study aimed to examine the teaching competence of secondary school teachers and to investigate if there are any significant differences between male and female secondary school teachers. The findings of the study indicate that a majority of the secondary school teachers have an average level of teaching competence. However, only a small percentage of secondary school teachers have a high and low level of teaching competence. Furthermore, the results of the study revealed a significant difference in the teaching competence of male and female secondary school teachers. Female teachers had a significantly higher mean score than male teachers, indicating that they possess a higher level

of teaching competence. This suggests that there might be some gender-based differences in the development of teaching competence, which needs to be further explored.

The present study has some limitations that need to be acknowledged. Firstly, the study was conducted in only one district, which may limit the generalizability of the findings to other districts. Secondly, the sample size was relatively small, which may limit the power of the study to detect significant differences. Finally, the study did not examine the factors that might contribute to the development of teaching competence in teachers, such as teacher education, teacher education curriculum and teacher evaluation. Despite these limitations, the present study provides some useful insights into the teaching competence of secondary school teachers. The findings suggest that there is a need to develop strategies to enhance the teaching competence of secondary school teachers, especially male teachers. The results also highlight the need for further research to explore the factors that might contribute to the development of teaching competence among secondary school teachers. Finally, this study adds to the growing body of research on teacher education and provides useful information that can be used to improve teacher education practices.

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